

The Simple Model of Newton's II Law and Its Applications

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ABSTRACT - The research aims to determine The Simple model for Newton's II Law and its application. The sample of this study is 20 sample variation. Data analysis technique used is by regression analysis. From the results of the analysis it was found that Freghitung=4,28 and Freg-table =4,13 (Freg-count >Freg-table), so the conclusion of this study is that there is a very large the simple model of Newton's II law and its application.

KEYWORDS- Simple Model; Newton's II Law; Newton's II Law Application

I. INTRODUCTION

Basic physics is one of the courses in semester 1 for engineering students. Physics has an important role in other subjects and as a preparatory course in semester 1 for engineering students. Newton's Second Law is one of the materials in basic physics that is studied for semester 1 engineering students. Newton's Second Law, which is one of Newton's III laws, is important material to understand [1]. Newton's Second Law is included in dynamics material which is widely used in everyday life including those related to object motion, object mass, object velocity, object acceleration and time [2].

Sir Isaac Newton (1643-1727) in his work *Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica* stated three laws about the motion of objects [3].

I. Every object will continue to be at rest or move at a constant speed along a straight path if it is not forced to change its state of motion by forces acting on it (Newton's First Law).

II. The resultant force acting on an object will result in a change in momentum. The change in momentum per unit time experienced by the object is directly proportional with the resultant force acting on it (Newton's Second Law).

III. If an object exerts a force (action) on another object, then the object subjected to the action will exert a force (reaction) on the first object which is the same magnitude but the direction is opposite to the force of action (Newton's III Law).

Computational physics is an integral part of the development of problems or physical phenomena and the ability to anticipate them using computer devices. Making simulations of these physical phenomena can be done with algorithms and computer programs. The application of computers in physics is seen in solving complex analytical problems and numerical tasks for interactive solutions. Therefore, computational physics offers a combination of

three disciplines and sciences, namely physics, numerical analysis and computer programming [4].

When viewed from the academic staff, there are still many teaching staff who are still reluctant to use computers, while computers are the main tool for the development of computational physics. In fact, more broadly, computers can be used as a tool for typing, data processing, experimentation or simulation tools, etc., supported by computer software capabilities [5], so that in general it can be said that the existence of computer technology can help the development of science physics.

The scope of the discussion mostly focuses on kinematics issues. Newton's Second Law can be used to help solve motion problems in one and two dimensions. Limiting the problem to one-dimensional and two-dimensional motion is not the final solution to all computational physics problems. Therefore, further studies are needed about the various physical symptoms that exist [6-7].

Whereas in terms of solving mathematical models there are constraints, such as linear mechanical vibrations N degrees of freedom, nonlinear mechanical vibrations, constrained particle motion in 2 and 3 dimensions, many-particle systems, analysis of rigid bodies for inhomogeneous bodies and arbitrary shapes, and gravitational fields by non-homogeneous objects and arbitrary shapes [8]. So, air resistance cannot be simply ignored. As an example are natural events that cannot ignore air friction, such as paratroopers, sky divers, jumping squirrels, and other small creatures that have also proven this [9-10].

II. METHODS

Methods compare simple model and practice. This method was chosen because researchers cannot control independent variables through manipulation or experimental treatment because treatment already exists and has occurred before by other people who are not researchers [11].

The test technique used to test the hypothesis in this study is regression analysis. This regression analysis is used to predict how far the value of the dependent variable changes if the value of the independent variable is manipulated/changed or increased and decreased [12].

The sequence of the algorithm is arranged as follows:

- Step 1. Determine the value for the interval h
- Step 2. Determine the initial velocity $v_0 = 0$
- Step 3. The while $t \leq t_{\max}$ loop
- Step 4. Calculate the acceleration with the equation $F = m \cdot a$

- Step 5. Print time t, acceleration a, and velocity v.
- Step 6. Multiply h and a and add the speed to get the new value of speed.
- Step 7. Increment the time with h.
- Step 8. Return to the loop in step 4 until t > tmax
- Step 9. Finish/Exit.

The general equation of simple linear regression is

$$Y = ax + b \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Then calculate the value of F using the formula:

$$F = S2reg / S2sis \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

F-count compared to F-table with dk quantifier = 1 and dk denominator = n-2 uses an error level of 5% with the criteria F-count > F-table [13]. Then determine the correlation coefficient between the two variables using the rough product moment correlation formula as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum X_i Y_i - (\sum X_i)(\sum Y_i)}{\sqrt{(n \sum X_i^2 - (\sum X_i)^2) (n \sum Y_i^2 - (\sum Y_i)^2)}} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

By criteria; if the price of Freg > Ftable with a significant level of 5% then the data is significant [14].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tabel 1: Data for Acceleration of fixed

No	Mess (kg)	Acceleration (ms ⁻¹)	F=m.a
1.	0,1	2	0,2
2.	0,2	4	0,8
3.	0,3	6	1,8
4.	0,4	8	3,2
5.	0,5	10	5,0
6.	0,6	12	6,0
7.	0,7	14	9,8
8.	0,8	16	12,8
9.	0,9	18	16,2
10.	1,0	20	20,0
Amount	0,55	9,8	7,58

Figure 1: Data for Acceleration not fixed

For the acceleration of objects that are not fixed, the Newton force is obtained which is getting bigger and bigger depending on the mass of the object [15].

Tabel 2: Data for Acceleration fixed

No	Mess(kg)	Acceleration (ms ⁻¹)	F=m.a
1.	0,1	2	0,2
2.	0,2	2	0,4
3.	0,3	2	0,6
4.	0,4	2	0,8
5.	0,5	2	1,0
6.	0,6	2	1,2
7.	0,7	2	1,4
8.	0,8	2	1,6
9.	0,9	2	1,8
10.	1,0	2	2,0
Amount	0,55	2	2,9

Figure 2: Data for Acceleration fixed

If the constant acceleration is taken as a sample of 2 ms⁻¹, the greater the Newtonian force, the longer it gets, depending on the mass of the object, which is also getting bigger.

this means that the Newtonian force and the mass of the object are directly proportional.

For large and varied data, this modeling program can help to understand and use it more easily. enough step-by-step program that has been made [16].

IV. CONCLUSION

For the acceleration of objects that are not fixed, the Newton force is obtained which is getting bigger and bigger depending on the mass of the object [15] and for large and varied data, this modeling program can help to understand and use it more easily. enough step-by-step program that has been made [16].

The Simple model for Newton's II Law and its application. The sample of this study is 20 sample variation. The research method used was practice and compare modeling. Engineering students' abilities in learning physics can be helped with simple modeling. Data analysis technique used is by regression analysis. From the results of the analysis it was found that Freg hitung = 4,28 and Freg-table = 4,13 (Freg-count > Freg-table), so the conclusion of this study is that there is a very large the simple model of Newton's II law and its application.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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